

Impact of Technology, Social Interaction, and Motivation on Employees' Commitment

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Abstract:

This article explores the impact of three independent variables, i.e. technology, social interaction, and motivation on employees' commitment to organizations hiring them as the sole dependent variable studied. This impact is investigated based on the main sub-constructs of the independent variables drawn from the operational definitions that enable the researcher to assess the impact accurately. The mixed research method, in which both qualitative and quantitative research tools were administered, was utilized for conducting the study. A sample of 300 instructors hired by private centers in a small city, i.e. Beni Suef, were recruited, out of the whole population of 500 instructors, for the study. A questionnaire was administered as a quantitative research tool for collecting numeric data whereas the interview was conducted as a qualitative research tool. Triangulation was used as a technique for attaining a deeper understanding of the data collected. Data collected was interpreted for drawing findings and conclusions leading to realizing the correlation attaching these variables altogether.

Keywords:

Employees' Commitment – Technology – Social Interaction – Motivation

Introduction:

Instructors represent the major asset of any organization. Successful organizations function with the aid of highly motivated and efficient employees (Gaur, Shukla & Verma, 2019). This optimum level of functionality can be attained via several factors that guarantee employees' commitment to the organization they work for. With the accelerating need to recruit efficient

employees, working on various variables affecting this performance is a priority. Providing the appropriate level of motivation to employees should be the main concern of the organization represented in human resources personnel. As well, both types of motivation have to be addressed adequately (Adebayo, 2021). Nevertheless, overcoming obstacles hindering performance, e.g. technology and social networking, has to be taken into consideration. Based on the three dimensions of employees' commitment to the organization presented by Al-Madi et al. (2017), i.e. affective, continuance, and normative organizational commitment, emotions, costs of leaving the organization, and obligation to the organization are the three variables influenced by employees' perception of the organization (Al-Madi et al., 2017).

Recent research asserts the impact of job satisfaction on employees' commitment. Basically, this satisfaction is manifested in motivation, i.e. intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Therefore, it is necessary to comprehend the major types of motivation affecting employees' performance (Saputra & Mahaputra, 2022). In various contexts, including educational businesses, the main concern of educational businesses is the extrinsic type of motivation. In educational businesses, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation affect instructors' commitment to the organization based on the level of satisfaction presented by the organization to the instructors. Successful human resources personnel can spot the right type of motivation affecting the candidate (Al-Madi et al., 2017). Meanwhile, working tools, mainly represented in using technological tools or equipment, as well as the organizational culture represented in the social

interaction among instructors and other personnel represent more factors affecting instructors' commitment to the organization they work for (Njenga, Kamau & Njenga, 2015). Technology is a major weakness point in several educational businesses in developing countries. As well, the organizational culture is not usually highlighted to new instructors.

The current study aims to investigate the impact of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on instructors' commitment to the educational business based on the Expectancy Theory understanding. As well, another objective of the current study is represented in investigating the impact of technological tools' usefulness and ease of use on instructors' commitment to the educational business based on the Technology Acceptance Model. Meanwhile, this was accompanied by investigating the impact of social interactions leading to interpersonal relationships among instructors on instructors' commitment to the educational business based on the Social Exchange Theory. Hence, there are three theoretical frameworks governing the structure of the study, i.e. Expectancy Theory, Technology Acceptance Model, and Social Exchange Theory.

These fundamental objectives lead to solid positive consequences resulting from completing the study. Major consequences are represented in providing an adequate understanding of the impact of motivation on instructors' performance which leads to a decrease in employee turnover; namely instructor turnover, in small and medium educational businesses; especially in small African cities. Another consequence is identifying issues related to using technology in educational businesses, mainly by instructors, based on their experiences; especially after adopting online and blended learning in several educational institutions. This leads to bridging the gap between instructors and various business owners and stakeholders who do not realize the reasons for this issue. Moreover, the current study leads to identifying the social factors and networks leading to the organizational culture that is not usually

identified and adequately presented to instructors in small and medium educational businesses. Meanwhile, this study addresses the major three variables affecting educational businesses in developing countries in one study. This will bridge this gap in the field of research conducted on educational businesses. Personal observations as well as the literature review reveal the necessity of addressing these variables for better instructors' commitment. This consequently leads to a higher level of job satisfaction which leads to higher profits.

Literature Review:

Technology:

Technology is defined in light of the foundational work of the Technology Acceptance Model presented by Davis (1989) and Venkatesh et al. (2003). Here, technology is defined by Davis (1989) in the light of Perceived Ease of Use as the level of difficulty of using technology as perceived by individuals which can be measured using questionnaires and interviews via which participants express their beliefs regarding easiness of using technology for fulfilling required tasks.

Meanwhile, Davis (1989) defines technology based on Perceived Usefulness as individuals' belief in the ability to use specific technology to improve their performance in the workplace. This component can be measured using self-reports to assess the positive impact of using specific technology for fulfilling specific tasks professionally. In addition, relevance to the task fulfilled can be also assessed.

As per defining technology in light of Behavioral Intention to Use, Davis (1989) presents this construct as a major component for presenting the definition. Here, technology is defined as the potential possibility of using relevant technology in the future as perceived by individuals. This can be measured using questionnaires and interviews to have a better understanding of individuals' intentions to adopt technology and adapt to it in the future. Venkatesh et al. (2003), however, define technology in light of Actual Use as the variable expressing the realistic use conduct related to

technology in the workplace. This necessitates assessing the duration, frequency, and extent to which technology is utilized. Questionnaires and interviews can be used to attain this goal.

As per *Attitude Towards Using Technology*, Venkatesh et al. (2003) present a definition leaning on several components represented in having access to hardware and software in the workplace for fulfilling tasks and achieving the goals required. In addition, the design of the interface and usability play a vital role in enhancing task performance in the business context. Other components include features of the technological tool, resources available for providing training and technical support, availability of merging technology used in daily tasks, and reliability of the technological tool utilized.

Social Interaction:

Definitions of social interaction in light of Social Exchange Theory have been presented via the foundational work of Emerson (1976), Thibaut & Kelley (1959), Cook & Emerson (1978) as well as Blau (1964). Definitions of social interaction are presented in light of the three components, i.e. Relationship Evaluation, Perceived Costs, and Perceived Rewards. Thibaut & Kelley (1959) define social interaction in light of Perceived Costs as the outcomes resulting from social interaction that can be negative. Operationally, social interaction can be assessed via examining participants' perceptions of the negative impact resulting from social interaction using questionnaires and interviews. Perceived Rewards, however, are presented by Emerson (1976) to be used for defining social interaction as the positive outcomes resulting from social interaction. Like Perceived Costs, Perceived Rewards can be measured using questionnaires and interviews to identify participants' perceptions of the desirable impact coming out of social interaction in the business context.

Cook & Emerson (1978) as well as Blau (1964), however, handle the definition of social interaction in light of Relationship Evaluation. Several components are identified for defining

social interaction in light of Relationship Evaluation. These components include patterns of communication, e.g. content, mode, and frequency of interaction among individuals in business contexts. Perceived relationship quality is another component that includes intimacy, satisfaction, and fulfillment as basic indicators governing social interaction within business contexts. A third component is represented in the reciprocity of engagement which refers to active participation and responsiveness in social contexts; especially business ones.

According to Blau (1964), the type of feedback received, i.e. constructive and negative feedback, has a major impact on social interaction in the business context. This can be translated into support, affirmation, and encouragement, on the one hand, as well as the negative feedback represented in criticism, conflict, or disagreement, on the other. Emotional tone as well as strategies used for resolving conflicts represent other components that affect social interaction in business contexts.

Motivation:

Definitions of motivation based on the Expectancy Theory were originally presented by Vroom (1964), the founder of the theory. In the light of Expectancy, i.e. Effort-Performance Expectancy, motivation is defined as the potential possibility of attaining a higher level of performance in fulfilling a specific task based on the efforts exerted. Hence, Vroom (1964) defines motivation operationally in the workplace as a variable that can be measured and assessed via directing questions to employees regarding their belief in the possibility of fulfilling tasks successfully via exerting the necessary efforts.

When attributing motivation to Instrumentality, Vroom (1964) defines it as the belief that a reward can come as a result of performing tasks successfully. This definition translates into an operational one when attributing it to the organizational context and assuming that motivation can be measured and assessed via

investigating employees' beliefs regarding the possibility of receiving incentives, getting promoted or receiving a reward based on the level of their performance when fulfilling various tasks.

When it comes to Valence, however, Vroom (1964) presents it as the Value of Rewards, i.e. how the reward is valuable or attractive based on the employees' point of view. Consequently, motivation is defined operationally as a variable that can be measured or assessed based on employees' preferences when it comes to the type of reward, e.g. promotion, incentives, bonuses...etc.

Employees' Commitment:

In the current study, commitment is studied in educational businesses as a dependent variable affected by motivation, technology, and social interaction. Commitment in the business environment is divided into several types, i.e. affective commitment, continuance commitment, Normative Commitment, and organizational commitment. Affective commitment is defined operationally as the limit of employees' attachment to the institution or the organization they work for which leads to a deeper level of involvement with the entity hiring them. This can be measured using questionnaires and interviews assessing affective commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991).

As per Continuance Commitment, it is operationally defined by Meyer & Allen (1991) as the negative outcomes resulting from leaving the organization as perceived by the employee. This is referred to as the perceived cost of leaving the organization. This can be measured using questionnaires and interviews assessing continuance commitment.

Meyer & Allen (1991) define Normative Commitment operationally as a third type of commitment referring to moral or ethical reasons leading employees to have a sense of duty to remain in the organization. This can be measured using questionnaires and interviews assessing normative commitment.

Accordingly, employees' commitment is defined operationally in the current study as the

dependent variable that can be measured using questionnaires and interviews assessing employees' perceptions of perceived costs, attachment to their organization as well as the sense of duty towards the entity they work for.

Objectives of the Study:

The current study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Investigating the impact of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on instructors' commitment to the educational business based on the Expectancy Theory understanding
- Investigating the impact of technological tools' usefulness and ease of use on instructors' commitment to the educational business based on the Technology Acceptance Model
- Investigating the impact of social interactions leading to interpersonal relationships among instructors on instructors' commitment to the educational business based on the Social Exchange Theory

Methodology and Data Collection:

Based on the problem addressed in the current study, i.e. the impact of motivation, technology, and social interaction on employees' commitment, the mixology research method design is utilized for approaching the research problem. This research design is more convenient for collecting more reliable data rather than solely depending on qualitative or quantitative research designs. Since the mixed research method is used in the current study, the data was collected using a questionnaire representing the numeric data collection tool needed for the quantitative research method as well as the interview as the non-numeric data collection tool used in qualitative research methods. Data collected via both tools was analyzed.

The current study necessitates using the mixed research method for the impracticality of using

either **solely to investigate** the research problem. Collecting data using quantitative tools, for instance, to assess the impact of one variable on the other lacks credibility since more data can be collected using qualitative research tools, e.g. focus groups or interviews. When answering questions from the questionnaire used in the pilot study, some participants showed an inability to decide on the choice that represents their case. Here, the interview provides further information and allows both the participants and the researcher to better understand the variables investigated. Here, the sole dependence on either tool makes the data collected unreliable. Therefore, utilizing the mixed research method is essential. Since the current study relies on the sequential transformative research design, which is a variation of the mixed research method, both qualitative and quantitative research tools were utilized for conducting the research. A questionnaire was utilized to assess the impact of motivation, technology, and social interaction on the employees' commitment. For the current study, a sample of instructors, representing employees, in some educational businesses was selected to study the impact of motivation, technology, and social interaction on their commitment to educational businesses. Instructors teach a variety of courses based on the needs of learners in specific areas.

As per the population out of which the sample has been selected, both part-time and full-time instructors responsible for providing various courses in private centers either online or in person represent the population addressed in the current study. The size of the population is estimated at 500 instructors with various demographic backgrounds. Population demography includes gender, both females and males are represented. Instructors belong to urban and rural communities. In addition, they teach several courses. As well, they belong to a range of age groups.

Since instructors represent the majority of the workforce in private centers, they possess the criteria matching the major criteria needed for the current study that investigates the

commitment of employees in educational businesses. In the meantime, this population is the idealistic one dealing with the three major variables of the study, i.e. motivation, technology, and social interaction since they usually represent two-thirds of the workforce in most private centers.

Variables of the Study:

Technology is an independent variable in the current study. It is measured based on the main constructs of the Technology Acceptance Model which have Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Towards Using Technology, Behavioral Intention to Use Technology, and Actual Usage Behavior as the main constructs.

Social interaction is an independent variable in the current study. It is measured based on the main constructs of the Social Exchange Theory which have three sub-constructs, i.e. Relationship Evaluation, Perceived Costs, and Perceived Rewards.

Motivation is an independent variable in the current study. It is measured based on the main constructs of the Expectancy Theory that have Expectancy, Instrumentality, and Valence as the main constructs.

Commitment is a dependent variable affected by motivation, technology, and social interaction. Commitment in the business environment is divided into several types, i.e. affective commitment, continuance commitment, Normative Commitment, and organizational commitment.

In addition to independent and dependent variables in the current study, there were extraneous variables that were controlled to ensure that only independent variables, handled in the study, affect the dependent variable addressed.

Data Analysis and Findings Discussion:

As per the questionnaire, items of the questionnaire had to be coded since verbal data related to demographic information, for instance, cannot be analyzed without coding. Each response was given a specific code to

facilitate the analysis process. According to Babbie (2016), responses of questionnaires can be given numerical codes. Each specific attribute is corresponded to a code.

The numeric scale from 1 to 5 was used to code the Likert-type questionnaire in an Excel sheet.

Here, codes go as follows:

1 corresponds to "Strongly Disagree"

2 corresponds to "Disagree"

3 corresponds to "Undecided"

4 corresponds to "Agree"

5 corresponds to "Strongly Agree"

Respondent ID	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
1	5	4	5	4	5
2	4	3	4	3	4
3	3	2	3	2	3
...

Here, each column (Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5) corresponds to a question, and respondents' answers are coded using the numerical scale. This format can be used to enter data for each participant.

Additionally, a separate sheet or section in the Excel file can be presented as a codebook that explains the numerical scale for each response. For instance:

Codebook:

Cod	Response
1	Strongly Dis
2	Disagree
3	Undecided
4	Agree
5	Strongly Ag

Table 1: Multiple Regression Analysis

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
E	3.4740	.10469	300
I	1.6840	.60644	300
V	2.4880	.38464	300
PU	4.3695	.33982	300
PEU	1.9920	1.05168	300
ATU	3.3465	.53808	300
BIU	3.5983	.37486	300
AUB	3.5808	.32596	300
RE	4.3011	.18268	300
PC	4.4470	.19395	300
PR	4.4530	.16180	300

Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics for several variables studied in the research (E, I, V, PU, PEU, ATU, BIU, AUB, RE, PC, and PR) in the context of multiple regression analysis. The previous table can be interpreted as follows. The mean represents the average value of each variable across all observations. For example, the mean for variable E is 3.4740, indicating the average value for E across the sample is approximately 3.47. As for Standard Deviation, it is a measure of the amount of variation or dispersion in a set of values investigated. A lower standard deviation indicates that the values tend to be close to the mean, while a higher standard deviation indicates more spread out values. The standard deviation for variable I, for instance, is 0.60644, suggesting that the values of I are somewhat distributed around the mean value.

Number of observations is represented in the symbol N. It refers to the number of observations or cases in the sample. In the current study, there are 300 observations for each variable. As per other variables, i.e. (E, I, V, PU, PEU, ATU, BIU, AUB, RE, PC, PR), they represent the variables included in the multiple regression analysis using the SPSS software. Each variable has its mean and

standard deviation. In multiple regression, these descriptive statistics provide a snapshot of the central tendency and variability of each variable in the data analyzed. Understanding these measures is crucial for assessing the

characteristics of the data before proceeding with the regression analysis. Table 2: Correlations

Table 2 shows the Pearson correlation

Table 2: Correlations

		E	I	V	PU	PEU	ATU	BIU	AUB	RE	PC	PR
Pearson Correlation	E	1.000	-.022	.037	.162	-.006	.012	-.033	.187	.090	-.083	.052
	I	-.022	1.000	.214	-.385	.116	.042	-.050	-.143	-.137	-.070	-.217
	V	.037	.214	1.000	-.204	-.299	.045	.313	.164	.134	.017	.118
	PU	.162	-.385	-.204	1.000	-.151	-.117	-.257	-.164	.211	.235	-.042
	PEU	-.006	.116	-.299	-.151	1.000	-.225	-.074	-.062	-.161	-.067	-.168
	ATU	.012	.042	.045	-.117	-.225	1.000	-.046	-.117	.025	-.037	-.007
	BIU	-.033	-.050	.313	-.257	-.074	-.046	1.000	.459	.094	.067	.082
	AUB	.187	-.143	.164	-.164	-.062	-.117	.459	1.000	-.094	-.226	.026
	RE	.090	-.137	.134	.211	-.161	.025	.094	-.094	1.000	.509	.208
	PC	-.083	-.070	.017	.235	-.067	-.037	.067	-.226	.509	1.000	.131
	PR	.052	-.217	.118	-.042	-.168	-.007	.082	.026	.208	.131	1.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	E	.	.350	.261	.002	.462	.420	.287	<.001	.059	.076
I		.350	.	.000	.000	.022	.234	.196	.007	.009	.115	.000
V		.261	.000	.	.000	.000	.221	.000	.002	.010	.385	.020
PU		.002	.000	.000	.	.004	.022	.000	.002	.000	.000	.233
PEU		.462	.022	.000	.004	.	.000	.100	.142	.003	.124	.002
ATU		.420	.234	.221	.022	.000	.	.212	.021	.332	.260	.455
BIU		.287	.196	.000	.000	.100	.212	.	.000	.052	.123	.078
AUB		.001	.007	.002	.002	.142	.021	.000	.	.052	.000	.325
RE		.059	.009	.010	.000	.003	.332	.052	.052	.	.000	.000
PC		.076	.115	.385	.000	.124	.260	.123	.000	.000	.	.011
PR		.185	.000	.020	.233	.002	.455	.078	.325	.000	.011	.
N		E	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	I	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	V	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	PU	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	PEU	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	ATU	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	BIU	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	AUB	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	RE	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	PC	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
	PR	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

coefficients between different variables investigated in the current study, i.e. (E, I, V, PU, PEU, ATU, BIU, AUB, RE, PC, PR) in the data analyzed. The correlation coefficients measure the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables. The table

can be interpreted as follows. As per correlation coefficients, a positive correlation coefficient indicates a positive linear relationship (as one variable increases, the other tends to increase). A negative correlation coefficient, however, indicates a negative linear relationship (as one

variable increases, the other tends to decrease). The closer the correlation coefficient is to +1 or -1, the stronger the linear relationship. A coefficient of 0 indicates no linear relationship. As for the Significant Correlations, the "Sig. (1-tailed)" values indicate the significance level of the correlation coefficients. If the p-value is less than the chosen significance level (commonly 0.05), the researcher rejects the null hypothesis of no correlation. In the row for variable 'PU' (perceived usefulness), for instance, there are correlations with other variables. The correlation between 'PU' and 'RE' is 0.211, and the p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant positive correlation.

The correlation between 'E' (expectancy) and 'PU' (perceived usefulness) is 0.162, suggesting a weak positive correlation. The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance. The correlation between 'I' (instrumentality) and 'V' (valence) is -0.385, indicating a moderate negative correlation. The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance. As well, the correlation between 'RE' (relationship evaluation) and 'PC' (perceived costs) is 0.509, indicating a moderate positive correlation. The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance. The bottom part of the table provides the number of observations (N) for each pair of variables.

To determine whether there is a significant correlation between motivation, technology, social interaction, and employees' commitment, the correlation coefficients and their corresponding p-values in the table should be examined. When investigating the correlation between the variables related to motivation, technology, and social interaction (E, I, V, PU, PEU, ATU, BIU, AUB) and the variable representing employees' commitment (RE), the following is observed. The correlation between 'E' (expectancy) and 'RE' (relationship evaluation) is 0.090, and the p-value is 0.059 (> 0.05). The correlation between 'I' (instrumentality) and 'RE' is -0.137, and the p-value is 0.009 (< 0.05). The correlation between

'V' (valence) and 'RE' is 0.134, and the p-value is 0.010 (< 0.05). Also, the correlation between 'PU' (perceived usefulness) and 'RE' is 0.211, and the p-value is < 0.001 . The correlation between 'PEU' (attitude towards using technology) and 'RE' is -0.161, and the p-value is 0.003. The correlation between 'ATU' (actual usage behavior) and 'RE' is 0.025, and the p-value is 0.332 (> 0.05). The correlation between 'BIU' (perceived costs) and 'RE' is 0.094, and the p-value is 0.052 (slightly above 0.05). The correlation between 'AUB' (perceived rewards) and 'RE' is -0.094, and the p-value is 0.052 (slightly above 0.05).

Based on these observations, there are some significant correlations between certain motivational, technological, and social interaction variables and employees' commitment. Notably, 'I,' 'V,' 'PU,' and 'PEU' have statistically significant correlations with 'RE.' It's important to note that correlation does not imply causation, and other factors could influence the observed relationships. Additionally, the significance level (alpha) chosen (commonly 0.05) affects the interpretation of p-values.

The previous analysis provides answers to the research questions provided earlier via assuming that there are statistically significant positive correlations between employees' commitment and the sub-constructs of motivation represented in expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. The same positive correlation exists between employees' commitment and the sub-constructs of technology represented in perceived usefulness, perceived ease of using technology, attitudes towards using technology, behavioral intention to use technology, and actual usage behavior. Additionally, the same statistically significant positive correlations exist between employees' commitment and the sub-constructs of social interaction represented in relationship evaluation, perceived costs, and perceived rewards.

As per the interview responses, 100 participants were interviewed. Responses were recorded for

later analysis. Data analysis procedures utilized the interview protocol provided earlier as well as the following steps. First, the interview responses were read thoroughly to be familiarized with them. This leads to understanding the context and patterns of responses emerging. Then, the responses collected were coded into categories based on a coding book. Here, initial themes and patterns are identified in light of the variables coded. This step was followed by interpreting data and identifying the themes related to the research objectives. Since the mixed research design was used in the current study, the triangulation technique was utilized. The data collected via the interview was compared to the data collected via the questionnaire to identify the common findings.

Investigating the data collected led to the following findings. When analyzing responses to questions addressing motivation, most responses expressed a tendency to have loyalty to the organization when receiving financial rewards in a way that matches the local economic situation. For instance, most participants were demotivated when offered low financial incentives. Nevertheless, they were highly motivated and committed to the organization when offered professional development opportunities as a reward.

As per questions addressing technology, participants were generally aware of the importance of using technology to attain their

professional goals. According to some participants, this was not the case prior to the lockdown. New developments encouraged most of them to have positive attitudes toward technology; especially when perceiving the new opportunities that they can seize the technological skills needed for competing in the local and the international marketplace.

Social interaction questions revealed the relation between this construct and the previous one, i.e. technology. Eagerness to utilize technology to the maximum encouraged participants to build powerful connections for exchanging experiences. However, it led also to a higher level of competitiveness among a few participants. Nevertheless, in both cases, participants had a higher level of commitment to organizations that provide a dynamic community to provide professional development and build powerful connections for further opportunities.

Hence, the results of the qualitative data analysis refer to the same conclusions drawn via the quantitative data analysis. The statistically significant correlation between the previously mentioned constructs and employees' commitment is even stronger when analyzing interview responses. Participants were allowed to express their ideas thoroughly. Moreover, follow-up questions were asked for further understanding.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a detailed account of all stages followed for conducting the research professionally. When it comes to conducting the research scientifically, there are three main stages, i.e. planning, implementation, and interpretation. In the planning phase, the mixed research method was assigned as the research methodology suiting the current study. Since this methodology depends on both qualitative and quantitative research techniques, the interview was assigned as the qualitative data collection tool that is used for collecting non-numerical data whereas the questionnaire was assigned as the numerical quantitative data collection tool. Data collected was analyzed using multiple regression statistical analysis utilizing SPSS software for evaluating the impact of the three independent variables on the dependent variable. Then, the findings are interpreted based on the research questions assigned earlier. Meanwhile, research ethics issues were addressed professionally to avoid any potential ethical misconduct. As well, extraneous variables were controlled for ensuring that the impact investigated is solely related to that of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

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